

Light pollution in Spain: policy brief

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Overview of the Problem, Its Scope, and Future Implications Without Action

Light pollution is defined as the "alteration of natural light levels" in the atmosphere, which can also occur in water or other mediums. This disruption leads to environmental impacts, including human health issues, and interferes with amenities and other legitimate uses of the environment. This definition stems from the "1979 Convention on Long-range Transboundary Air Pollution" and was explicitly discussed in the UN Report of the International Law Commission during its sixty-seventh session.

One significant issue with light pollution is the inconsistent definitions across various regulations. For instance, Spain's "Ley 34/2007, de 15 de noviembre, de calidad del aire y protección de la atmósfera" mirrors the definition of air pollution from the 1979 Convention, naturally including light pollution. However, it introduces a specific definition of light pollution that contradicts its own general air pollution definition by considering the usefulness of light. This inconsistency, influenced by the lighting industry lobby, is also evident in some EU documents.

Light pollution has widespread environmental impacts, affecting all species that rely on the day-night cycle to regulate hormonal cycles, rest, or navigate. Nighttime light disrupts these natural processes, creating physical barriers for many species. Despite its benefits in providing nighttime visibility and a sense of security, the ecological consequences are significant.

Until 2012, Spain had the highest rates of light pollution per capita and per streetlight in the EU. However, due to limitations in satellite data, lack of national statistics, and erroneous estimates from sources like IDAE and the Ministerio de Industria y Comercio, accurate data on energy consumption and light emissions from 2012 to 2021 is unavailable. Current estimates are expected to remain stable until 2017. New data from SDGSAT-1 and the International Space Station (ISS) is being analyzed to provide updated figures from 2010 to 2024.

Globally, light pollution is increasing at rates between 2.2% and 10% annually, with a minimum increase of 49% from 1992 to 2017. However, these figures are likely underestimations due to satellite data limitations, with actual values potentially up to 400% higher, especially regarding blue light content. Alternative data sources, such as SDGSAT-1 and ISS, are crucial for resolving these uncertainties.

The transition from High-Pressure Sodium (HPS) lamps to LEDs has introduced significant challenges. While LEDs are touted for their energy efficiency, their outdoor use is controversial. Issues such as the rebound effect from cheaper light sources and increased blue emissions are problematic. Despite recommendations from the IDAE, the lack of a comprehensive Life Cycle Cost analysis for new lighting installations exacerbates the problem.

Without action, light emissions will continue to increase, disrupting essential ecological services like pollination. Furthermore, significant public funds will be wasted on outdated technologies,

resulting in resource depletion and increased CO2 emissions. Addressing these issues requires coherent policies, accurate data, and a focus on sustainable lighting solutions.

Scientific Consensus and Disagreements on the Causes and Consequences of Light Pollution

There is broad scientific agreement on the primary causes of light pollution:

1. **Utility of Light:** Artificial lighting is widely used for safety, security, and convenience.
2. **Lack of Awareness:** Many people are unaware of the environmental and health impacts of light pollution.
3. **Fear of Darkness:** Psychological and cultural fears of darkness drive the demand for constant lighting.
4. **Status and Advertising:** Bright lighting is often used for status symbols and commercial advertising.
5. **Lack of Enforcement:** Insufficient enforcement of regulations exacerbates the problem.

There is substantial consensus on the environmental impacts of light pollution:

1. **Disruption of Ecosystems:** Light pollution disrupts natural behaviours in wildlife, such as migration, foraging, and reproduction.
2. **Circadian Rhythms:** The day-night cycle, crucial for many species' hormonal regulation and rest, is disturbed by artificial lighting.

While there is a consensus that lighting can provide a sense of safety, research indicates that the actual impact on crime reduction in developed countries is minimal or even negative. Well-designed studies generally show no significant benefits or adverse effects from increased lighting in terms of safety.

The scientific community remains divided on some health impacts of light pollution:

1. **Circadian Disruption:** There is agreement that extreme circadian disruption can be harmful. The World Health Organization (WHO) classifies such disruption as probably carcinogenic (Group 2A).
2. **Chronic Conditions:** There is ongoing debate about the extent to which light pollution may contribute to diseases such as cancer, diabetes, heart disease, and obesity. More research is needed to establish a clear connection.
3. **Glare and Vectors:** The negative impacts of glare on human vision and the promotion of disease vectors like mosquitoes are well-established.

The scientific community advocates for the establishment of a robust monitoring scheme to control light pollution effectively. Additionally, there is a recognized need for scientific foundations in current lighting standards to ensure they are based on sound research and effectively mitigate light pollution's adverse effects.

There is limited but promising evidence regarding regulations that effectively control light pollution. Here are some notable examples:

1. **La Palma and North of Tenerife Law:** This regulation has been demonstrably effective in reducing light pollution, setting a benchmark for other regions.
2. **French and Italian Laws:** These laws impose limits on total emissions and specifically restrict the percentages of blue light emitted.

Promising Practices and Measures

1. **Promotion of Good Practices:** Recently, IDAE has promoted the use of LEDs with no blue light emission, which represents a significant step towards reducing light pollution.
2. **Environmental Impact Assessments:** Implementing environmental impact assessments for nearly all installations can also mitigate light pollution. Given that many installations impact Natura 2000 reserves either directly or indirectly, these assessments are crucial.

Conclusion:

While there is a need for more widespread and consistent evidence of effective regulations, the examples from La Palma, Tenerife, France, and Italy provide valuable insights. Promoting good practices, requiring environmental impact assessments, and enhancing public awareness and enforcement can significantly contribute to mitigating light pollution. Addressing these issues requires improved public awareness, better enforcement of regulations, and scientifically grounded lighting standards.

Sources and justification:

More than 30 references have been used. That cannot fit on 3 pages. An extended version of this policy brief has been created where each statement is traceable. This way if the evidence gets outdated can be easily fixed. There are no available review articles about the situation of Spain and its neighbours:

Sánchez de Miguel, A. (2024). Extended Brief Policy Report in Spain: Light Pollution. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12677125>

This is a recent policy document in Spanish:

Del CSIC, P. (2024, June). Contaminación lumínica. Los peligros de un mundo cada vez más iluminado. Editorial CSIC. <http://doi.org/10.20350/DIGITALCSIC/16385>

This is a systematic review of the current knowledge on light pollution globally:

Barentine, J. (2024). Artificial Light at Night: State of the Science 2024. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11431447>

NOTE: the spelling of this text has been improved by chatGPT 4o.